

A Cross-Sectional Study on Dietary Habits Associated with Hypertension among Bus Drivers in Tamil Nadu

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hypertension is a major modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular and renal disease in India, and improved detection and treatment of hypertension in India would reduce a preventable burden of cardiac, cerebrovascular and renal disease related to hypertension. It has been estimated that a 2 mm population wide decrease in systolic blood pressure in India, would prevent 151,000 deaths due to coronary artery disease and 153,000 deaths due to stroke would be prevented. **Objectives:** To identify the prevalence of hypertension among bus drivers. To find out associated dietary habits with hypertension among bus drivers. **Methodology:** This is a community based cross sectional study conducted to bus drivers to identify the prevalence of hypertension and their dietary habits. Predesigned pretested questionnaire was used with study variable including sociodemographic details, addiction, diet habits, calorie and protein consumption by 24 hr recall method. **Results:** With the sample size of 400, nearly 91 study participants were known to have hypertension in which prevalence of hypertension among bus drivers was 22.8%. Addiction habits including alcohol 51 (28.3%) and tobacco 32 (26.9%) consumption with hypertension showed that they are not statistically significant with P value of .016 and .199 respectively. Type of diet including vegetarian, non-vegetarian and mixed diet was not statistically significant with hypertension of P-value 0.492. 57.4% are obese with hypertension among the study participants. BMI (Body Mass Index) was strongly associated with hypertension among bus drivers with P value of 0.000. **Conclusion:** This study highlighted that 22.8% of participants were known case of hypertension and they are not associated with diet type and addiction habits. Dietary habits and lifestyle disorders like obesity is associated with hypertension.

Key words: Hypertension, bus drivers, dietary habits, BMI (Body Mass Index), Addiction habits.

Introduction:

An estimated 1.28 billion adults aged 30 - 79 years worldwide have hypertension, most (two-thirds) living in low- and middle-income countries. Hypertension is a major cause of premature death worldwide. One of the global targets for noncommunicable diseases is to reduce the prevalence of hypertension by 33% between 2010 and 2030. Lifestyle changes like eating a healthier diet, quitting tobacco and being more active can help lower blood pressure.¹ Hypertension is a major modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular and renal disease in India, and improved detection and treatment of hypertension in India would reduce a preventable burden of cardiac (congestive heart failure, coronary artery disease), cerebrovascular (ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke) and renal (chronic kidney disease) disease related to hypertension.² Hypertension is a non-communicable disease (NCD) that significantly contributes to the rising incidence of cardiovascular conditions, leading to increased morbidity and mortality within the population.³

It has been estimated that a population wide decrease in 2 mm systolic blood pressure in India, would prevent 151,000 deaths due to coronary artery disease and 153,000 deaths due to stroke would be prevented. Bus drivers and conductors often face a range of health issues resulting from stressful and demanding working conditions.²

Over the past four decades, India has undergone significant lifestyle changes driven by urbanization and nutritional transitions linked to economic development. These changes have led to a rising prevalence of cardiovascular diseases (CVD), including hypertension and dyslipidemia. High dietary intake of salt and fat, along with increasingly sedentary lifestyles, are major contributing risk factors for both hypertension and dyslipidemia among Indian patients.²¹

India's economy relies significantly on the transportation sector, encompassing both public and private transport professionals such as truck drivers, bus conductors, taxi drivers, and autorickshaw operators. However, these workers frequently face numerous occupational health hazards, including long working hours, exposure to air pollution, irregular sleep patterns, and persistent stress.¹⁰ Prolonged exposure to occupational hazards contributes to the gradual decline of their overall health.¹¹

Aim and objectives:

To identify the prevalence of hypertension among bus drivers.

To find out associated dietary habits with hypertension among bus drivers.

Materials and methods:

This is a community based cross sectional study conducted to bus drivers in Chennai who are registered bus drivers in Tamil Nadu Road Transport Corporation to identify the prevalence of hypertension and their dietary habits, which was planned on October 2024 – February 2025 among bus drivers in Tamil Nadu. On the study done by Sasikaladevi et al in Chennai showed prevalence of hypertension was 49.5%. By which the study sample was calculated by prevalence study sample calculation with 95% CI & 5% precision and the sample size is 385, which was rounded to 400.

After getting the approval from institutional ethical committee, a predesigned pretested questionnaire was used to collect the data. The study participants were included in the study after getting their consent. Exclusion criteria include who were on chronic leave and not available during all the 7 consecutive visits during collection. The study proforma includes their socio demographic details, working experience, addiction habits, dietary habits and calculated their height, weight and BMI.

Smoking was defined as the use of any tobacco product in smoked form within the past six months, while alcohol use was defined as the consumption of any type of alcoholic beverage within the past year.⁴ Subjects were labelled hypertensive if systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mm Hg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mm Hg or taking antihypertensive medication.⁴

Dietary questionnaire was taken by 24 hr recall method for 7 days calorie and protein calculation. The average value of 7 days consumed cooked food and protein value were taken for calculation. Their daily calorie and protein consumption was followed up for 7 consecutive days and documented by google sheet. The required kcal for moderate work in reference adult man as per ICMR 2020 is 2710 Kcal¹² per day. Those who are consumed less than the required kcal and protein are considered deficit and who consumed more than the required kcal and protein are considered excess. Their height was measured using vertical

measuring tape attached to flat surface of the wall. Body weight was measured using electronic weighing scale. Participants were instructed to remove their shoes and any bulky clothing before a single measurement was taken, accurate to the nearest 100 grams.

Body mass index is defined as the weight in kilograms divided by the square of the height in meters (kg/m^2). The classification shown is in agreement with that recommended by WHO which follow as, Underweight < 18.50 , Normal range $18.50 - 24.99$, Overweight ≥ 25.00 , Obesity ≥ 30 .¹²

The collected data were systematically entered in MS Excel software. The data was analysed using Epi-info (version-7.2.5.0) software. Descriptive statistics were presented in terms of tables and figures. Frequency, percentages and chi-square were calculated for the variables.

Results:

In the present study, 400 bus drivers were included as study participants, in which 45.5% study population were in the age group of 40-49 yrs and 27.5% were in the age group of 30 - 39yrs. The mean age and Standard deviation were 43.25 ± 7.36 . Study subjects showed that 45.8% participants completed higher secondary, 31.3% were studied till high school and 20.5% were graduates. Nearly, 40.3% of bus drivers having experience of service in between 11-20yrs, followed by 32.4% in between 1-10yrs, 26.3% were having experience for 21-30yrs. The mean duration of the experience is 15.45 ± 7.9 . Regarding the type of diet, 80.3% were taking mixed diet, 14.3% were vegetarian and 5.4% were non-vegetarian. As shown in the Fig:1, 56.5% of study population consuming vegetables for 3-5 times per day. In the Fig:2 almost, 83.5% were taking fruits less than 3 times in a day. Nearly 45% of the study populations were consuming alcohol as shown in Fig:3. Only 29.8% of the study populations were smoker. Among the study participants, 63% of the study participants are overweight and 11.8% are obese as shown in the Fig:4.

The prevalence of hypertension among the bus drivers is 22.8%. The relation between age group and hypertension among the study participants, 50% were in between the age group of 50 – 59 yrs who were suffering from hypertension, as the age advances the disease frequency was increased and this was statistically significant as p value was 0.000 ($p < 0.001$). (Table: 1). Among the 24 % of the study participants consuming mixed diet were suffering from hypertension and 17.5% of vegetarians were also suffering from hypertension, which was

statistically not significant with the type of diet they consume with hypertension. (Table: 2). In assessing the addiction habits, 28.3% of study participants consuming alcohol were hypertension, whereas only 18.2% of hypertensive study participants were nonalcoholic and this was statistically significant with P- value 0.016. On finding the association between smoking and hypertension among the study participants, 26.9% of the smoker were having hypertension, it was little higher when comparing with participants those who were not smoker and this was not statistically significant as shown in Table:3.

As per 24-hour recall method, an average of 7 days the calorie and protein calculation were calculated and average value has been taken into consideration. The categorized value for calorie and protein resulted as deficit 4.2% & 10.5%, normal 5.1%, 3.7% and excess 13.5%, 8.7% in hypertensive study participants. The association between calorie and protein consumption with hypertensive study participants were found to be statistically significant with hypertensive study participants with P value <0.01.(Table:4). While focusing on Body Mass Index, nearly half of obese participants 57.4% were having hypertension comparing with overweight participants 18.3% and average Body Mass Index participants 17.8% and it was statistically significant (p=0.000) (Table :5).

Discussion:

The present study found that the prevalence of hypertension and associated dietary habits among bus drivers. In our study, the mean age and standard deviation was 43.25 ± 7.36 , which was similar to the study done by Rao CR et al to transport employee in Manipal stated that the mean age and standard deviation of the study population was 40.2 ± 9.2 years.⁸ A review written by Arun R and Stanly AM mentioned that there is a strong correlation between hypertension and age more than 35 years.^{14,21} In our study, almost 50% of the study participants with hypertension were aged above 50yrs and was found to be statistically significant with increased age group. The educational status of the study participants in this current study presented with 2.5% completed middle school, 45.8% are with the qualification of higher secondary, 31.3% were studied till high school and 20.5% were graduates. In a study done by Ali KBM et al¹¹ on Predictors for diabetes and hypertension among bus drivers and conductors in South India in 2014 also found that there is similar educational status of higher secondary completed bus drivers of 47.1%.

A study was conducted among young male bus drivers in Bengaluru, 2018 on comparison with waist-hip ratio, prehypertension and hypertension by Pushpa K and Kanchana R, stated that the drivers with job experience have increased Systolic and Diastolic blood pressure and was found to be statistically significant ($P = 0.001$)³. In the present study nearly 40.3% of the study participants were between job experience of 11- 20 yrs. The mean duration of service of bus drivers was 17.90 ± 8.85 years in North Goa by a study conducted by Vernekar SP et al in 2021⁵. Similarly in our current study, the mean duration of the experience among bus driver was 15.45 ± 7.9 .

In our study, almost 56.5% of study population consumed vegetables for 3-5 times per day which there is moderate awareness about diet consumption. Whereas, 1.7 million deaths and 16 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) worldwide are attributed to insufficient intake of green leafy vegetables and fruits. Adequate consumption of these foods can help reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases and gastrointestinal cancers¹⁸. In our present study, 80.3% were consuming mixed diet, 14.3% were vegetarian. 57.6% of commercial bus drivers were non vegetarian as by study done by Rawat SK et al¹⁶, here almost, 80.3% of bus drivers were mixed diet consumers in the present study. In a study done by Devarasu U et al in Coimbatore for bus drivers resulted that nearly 51% were consuming mixed diet and 35.6% were vegetarian.⁶

According to the addiction habits in our present study, about 46% of the study participants were found to be alcoholic. Whereas the study conducted by Kulkarni P et al in 2023 stated that 61.5% of their study participants were alcoholic among E- rickshaw drivers.¹⁷ But 16.8% were alcoholic in the study done by Sukumar GM et al among cab drivers in 2024 Bengaluru¹⁵. About, 67.2% were smoker on a mixed method study among transport workers in Karikal done by Ali KM et al in 2024¹⁰, whereas in the present study 29.8% were smokers. In 2015, a study done by Udayar SE et al for-transport drivers on hypertension associated with addiction habits, duration of alcohol intake and duration of tobacco use was found to be statistically significant with P-value 0.04.⁷ In the present study addiction habits, alcohol and hypertension among study subjects were statistically significant ($p = 0.016$). But smoking and hypertension among bus drivers in our study was not statistically significant with P value 0.199.

A systematic review and metaanalysis done for low- and middle-income bus drivers by Njiro BJ et al stated that the weighted prevalence of hypertension among professional drivers

was 36.7% (95% CI: 31.8–41.6%).⁹ In the current study the prevalence of hypertension among bus driver was found to be 22.8%. Randhawa S et al conducted a study among truck drivers in three regions of India, resulted that 47% of the truck drivers had raised blood pressure above normal.¹³ Approximately, 63% of the study participants are overweight and 11.8% are obese in the current study. In a study done by Jayarajah U et al in 2017 among bus drivers found that a total of 48.3% (95% CI 39.3% to 57.4%) were either overweight or obese.¹⁹ Increased consumption of high-energy foods particularly packaged and processed products high in fats and sugars - contributes to the rising prevalence of obesity.¹⁸ Obesity was significantly correlated with hypertension, with obese individuals having a 36% increased risk (OR: 1.36; P = 0.033) in the study done by Devarasu U et al.⁶ In our study 57.4% were obese and having hypertension comparing with overweight participants of 18.3% and average Body Mass Index participants of 17.8% and it was statistically significant (p=0.000). Central obesity has strongly associated with hypertension with a significant P value 0.003⁶ which was similar to our study.

Conclusion:

The present study has noted that considerable proportion of hypertension are accounted in bus driver population. This proportion may increase in near future that would reduce their quality of life as well as efficiency of expected skill from the drivers which protect the larger number of lives. The factors like overweight and obesity are associated with hypertension which can be effectively prevented. Hypertension should be controlled among the drivers as they may cause sudden collapse while they are driving.

Recommendation:

The study participants can be provided a healthy food options in workplace and dietary guidance can be initiated. Age targeted screening programs on noncommunicable disease like hypertension and awareness program on addiction habits are recommended. The dietary assessment details can be made by dietary index which can give a clear representation of dietary habits on hypertensive study participants with larger sample for generalizing the study.

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Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest

Reference

1. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hypertension>.
2. Screening, Diagnosis, Assessment, and Management of Primary Hypertension in Adults in India. Ministry of Health & Family Welfare Government of India. February 2016.
https://nhm.gov.in/images/pdf/guidelines/nrhm_guidelines/stg/Hypertension_full.pdf
3. Pushpa K, Kanchana R. Comparison of waist-hip ratio, prehypertension, and hypertension in young male bus drivers and non-drivers of Bengaluru city. *Natl J Physiol Pharm Pharmacol* 2018;9(1):90-94.
4. Suguna A, Surekha A, Boratne VA, Venkataraman S. Transport sector and cardiovascular disease risk estimation: cross-sectional analysis based on WHO/ISH chart. *Nat J Res Community Med* 2019;8(1): 50-54
5. Vernekar SP, Shah HK. A comparative study of cardiovascular disease risk among bus drivers and bus conductors of a state transport corporation in North Goa. *Int J Community Med Public Health* 2021;8:3023-9.
6. Devarasu U, Jayaraj NP, Sugunadevi G, Kokila K. Hypertension and lifestyle determinants in public transport drivers: A sector specific study in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu. *Acta Med Int* 2024;11
7. Udayar SE, Kumar RK, Kumar PBA, Vairamuthu S, Thatuku S. Study of Cardiovascular Risk Factors Among Transport Drivers in Rural area of Andhra Pradesh. *Ntl J of Community Med* 2015;6(4):566-570.
8. Rao CR, Kumar U, Mishra S, Kamath V. Screening for Non-Communicable Diseases among transport employees of a university: a descriptive analysis. *Indian J Comm Health*. 2016;28(1):100 - 105.

9. Njiro BJ, Ndumwa HP, Waithera HW, Chande R, Julius W, Mashili F, Mwita JC, Swahn MH, Staton C, Francis JM. Epidemiology of non-communicable diseases among professional drivers in LMICs: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Health Promotion International* 2024; 39.
10. Ali KM, Gnanamani G, Rahman KM, Nancy S. A Comprehensive assessment of occupational and lifestyle determinants of overweight and obesity among transport workers in Karaikal: A mixed-methods study. *Cuest.fisioter.*2024;53(3):1259-1273.
11. Ali KBM, Kumar SS, Govindarajan PK, Rahman KBM, Nancy S. Predictors for diabetes and hypertension among bus drivers and conductors in South India. *Bioinformation.* 2024;20(5):495-501.
12. Park K. Text book of preventive and social medicine. 26th ed. Jabalpur: M/s Banarasidas Bhanot Publishers. March 2021.
13. Randhawa S, Dogra V, Bambrah HS, Hedge S, Sudke AK, Phanse V. Morbidity profile and prevalence of diabetes and high blood pressure among truck drivers in three regions of India. *ResearchGate.* 2020;9(1):1 -16.
14. Arun R, Meriton Stanly A. A Review of Risk Factors for Non-Communicable Diseases Among Bus Drivers. *Natl J Community Med* June 2022;13(6):404-410.
15. Sukumar GM, Parivallal MB, Giboy SL, Thakkar AN. Work environment adversity and non-communicable Disease risk among drivers working for application-based-cab aggregators in an Indian metropolis. *BMC public health.* 2024;24(1592):1-9.
16. Rawat SK, Naagar JK, Agrawal R, Mishra S, Saad T, Mishra N, Mishra S, Singh P. Prevalence and Lifestyle associated risk factors of Hypertension and Diabetes among Commercial Professional Drivers: A Cross-sectional Study from Central India. *J Cardiovasc Dis Res.* 2023;14(12):500-512.
17. Kulkarni P, Parmar V, Jain S, Singh N, Gaur RJ. Evaluation of Socio-demographic Profile, Working Condition and Health of E-rickshaw Drivers in Udaipur City. *SSR Inst Int J Life Sci.,* 2024; 10(2): 5192 5197.
18. Varela-Mato V, Yates T, Stensel DJ, Biddle SJH, Clemes SA. Time spent sitting during and outside working hours in bus drivers: A pilot study. *Prev Med Rep.* Jun 2016;3:36–9.

19. Jayarajah U, Jayakody AJA, Jayaneth MBJN, Wijeratne S. Prevalence of hypertension and its associated factors among a group of bus drivers in Colombo, Sri Lanka. *Int J Occup Environ Med* 2017;8:58-59.
20. Burt VL, Whelton P, Roccella EJ, Brown C, Cutler JA, Higgins M, Horan MJ, Labarthe D. Prevalence of hypertension in the US adult population. Results from the Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, 1988-1991. *Hypertens Dallas Tex* 1979. 1995 Mar;25(3):305-13.
21. Anchala R, Kannuri NK, Pant H, Khan H, Franco OH, Di Angelantonio E, Prabhakaran D. Hypertension in India: a systematic review and meta-analysis of prevalence, awareness, and control of hypertension. *J Hypertens* 2014; 32:1170-7.

Table 1: Age Distribution of study participants with Hypertension

Age Group (in yrs)	HYPERTENSION		Total	P. Value
	Yes	No		
20 - 39	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	16 (100%)	$\chi^2 = 60.8$ d.f = 3 P = .000
30 - 39	7 (6.4%)	103 (93.6%)	110(100%)	
40 - 49	38 (20.9%)	144 (79.1%)	182 (100%)	
50 - 59	46 (50%)	46 (50%)	92 (100%)	
Total	91 (22%)	309 (77.2%)	400 (100%)	

Table 2: Type of diet among study subjects with Hypertension

Type of Diet	HYPERTENSION		Total	P. Value
	Yes	No		
Vegetarian	10 17.5%	47 82.5%	57 100%	$\chi^2 = 1.42$ d.f = 2 p = 0.2334
Non- Vegetarian	4 18.2%	18 81.8%	22 100%	
Mixed Diet	77 24%	244 76%	321 100%	
Total	91 22.8%	309 77.2%	400 100%	

Table 3: Addiction habits associated with Hypertension

Addiction Habits	HYPERTENSION			Total	P. Value
		YES	NO		
Alcohol	Yes	51 28.3%	129 71.7%	180 100%	$\chi^2 = 5.81$ d.f = 1 p = .016
	No	40 18.2%	180 81.8%	220 100%	
Total		91 22.8%	309 72.2%	400 100%	
Smoking	Yes	32 26.9%	87 73.1%	119 100%	
	No	59 21.0%	222 79.0%	281 100%	
Total		91 22.8%	309 77.2%	400 100%	

Table 4: Calorie and Protein consumption associated with Hypertension

Protein	Deficit	42(10.5%)	75(18.6%)	117	$\chi^2 = 21.4457$ P value - 0.000.
	Normal	15(3.7%)	36(9%)	51	
	Excess	35(8.7%)	198(49.5%)	233	
Total	91(22.8%)	309(77.2%)	400(100%)		
Calorie	Deficit	17(4.2%)	34(8.4%)	51	$\chi^2 = 8.2274$ P value - 0.0041
	Normal	21(5.1%)	47(11.8%)	68	
	Excess	53(13.5%)	228(57%)	281	
Total	91 (22.8%)	309 (77.2%)	400 (100%)		

Table 5: Body mass Index associated with Hypertension

BMI	HYPERTNSION		Total	P Value
	Yes	No		
18.5 - 24.99	18 17.8%	83 82.2%	101 100%	$\chi^2 = 36.5$ d.f = 2 p = .000
25 - 29.99	46 18.3%	206 81.7%	252 100%	
≥ 30.00	27 57.4%	20 42.6%	47 100%	
Total	91 22.8%	309 77.2%	400 100%	

Fig 1: Frequency of vegetables consumed by Bus Drivers

Fig 2: Frequency of fruits consumed by Bus Drivers

Fig 3: Alcohol Consumption among Bus Drivers

Fig 4: BMI categories among Bus Drivers